

Evaluation of Power Saving Achieved by Rotor Sail Systems for Very Large Ore Carriers

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Abstract. This study presents a comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis to evaluate the aerodynamic performance and power-saving potential of a rotor sail system installed on a full-scale Very Large Ore Carrier (VLOC). The simulation framework incorporates realistic atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) wind profiles, apparent wind conditions, rotor operational constraints, and aerodynamic interactions between the rotor sails and the ship hull. Convergence testing and model validation were conducted to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the CFD results. The analysis showed that rotor-generated net thrust is maximized when the apparent wind angle approaches 90°, and scales proportionally with the square of the true wind speed. However, rotor RPM limitations at high wind speeds constrain further performance gains. The study also revealed that hull-induced flow distortions influence rotor effectiveness based on location and wind direction. Additionally, lateral forces were found to increase significantly with wind speed, raising potential concerns regarding vessel maneuverability. Route-based power-saving assessments, using wind data from the ERA5 hindcast model, yielded average net power savings of 283 kW and 309 kW for the Brazil–East Asia and Brazil–Europe routes, respectively—equivalent to 1.8–2.0% of calm water propulsion power. These similar results are attributed to comparable apparent wind conditions across both routes. As the estimates are based on hourly net power rather than annual saving, the findings offer route-specific, practical insights to support shipowners in making informed decisions regarding rotor sail implementation. Overall, the study provides both technical understanding and operational guidance for applying rotor sail systems on large commercial vessels

Keywords: Rotor sail, Computational Fluid Dynamics, Power Saving.

1. Background

The maritime industry faces increasing pressure to improve fuel efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions as international regulations tighten. Wind-assisted propulsion technologies have re-emerged as promising solutions, with rotor sails (Flettner rotors) gaining particular attention as an effective means of harnessing wind power through the Magnus effect. A rotor sail is a powered spinning cylinder that generates lift perpendicular to the wind flow, augmenting a vessel's thrust. Early trials of this concept date back to the 1920s, but modern advances and successful installations (e.g., by Norsepower) have demonstrated significant fuel savings potential—typically ranging from 5% to 20% under favorable conditions [1]—renewing interest in rotor sails as a viable emissions-reduction technology. This background underscores the growing motivation to quantitatively evaluate rotor sail performance on contemporary cargo ships.

Several numerical studies have recently investigated the aerodynamic performance of rotor sails using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), examining how design and operating parameters influence the generated forces. De Marco et al. (2016) [2] performed steady-state Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) CFD simulations to systematically vary key rotor design parameters—including spin ratio, aspect ratio, and the presence of end plates—and characterized the resulting lift and drag coefficients. Their study demonstrated that increasing spin ratios and aspect ratios enhances lift, and that end plates (Thom disks) improve aerodynamic efficiency by mitigating tip vortices. Kwon et al. (2022) [3] extended these analyses through additional parametric CFD investigations of standalone rotors, exploring a wide range of spin ratios and geometric configurations to assess their effects on aerodynamic forces and torque requirements. These studies provided valuable preliminary performance predictions for rotor sails under idealized conditions.

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Despite these advances, most existing research has been limited to simplified geometries, small-scale models, or generalized wind conditions [2]. For instance, previous studies typically considered isolated rotors in uniform oncoming flow, often neglecting the presence of the ship’s hull and the variability of atmospheric wind profiles [3]. While some studies have attempted to apply higher-fidelity CFD approaches to refine rotor sail performance predictions, such efforts often remained confined to simplified single-rotor setups and steady-state assumptions [4]. Similarly, empirical and semi-empirical predictions frequently relied on fixed apparent wind angles or laboratory-scale Reynolds numbers [1]. Consequently, significant uncertainties persist when extrapolating these findings to full-scale ships operating in real environmental conditions [5].

Recent efforts have sought to bridge this gap. Tillig and Ringsberg (2020) [4] compared CFD predictions with sea trial data from ships equipped with rotor sails, revealing that while numerical models can capture general trends, real-world deviations often arise due to hull–rotor interactions and fluctuating atmospheric conditions. More recently, Sampaio et al. (2024) [5] advanced the field by conducting full-scale CFD simulations of a 325,000 DWT very large ore carrier (VLOC) fitted with five rotor sails, incorporating 40 years of ERA5 hindcast wind data to probabilistically assess system performance. Their study emphasized the influence of hull-induced flow distortion, rotor–rotor interference, and deckhouse turbulence on thrust variability, and highlighted the importance of optimizing spin ratio under realistic conditions. However, their approach primarily focused on long-term probabilistic trends rather than directly quantifying time-resolved net power savings for specific voyages.

Building upon these insights and addressing the remaining gaps, the present study distinguishes itself by constructing detailed aerodynamic performance polar diagrams from full-scale CFD simulations and integrating them into a ship performance model. This methodology enables the direct estimation of hourly net power savings across different trade routes, providing practical and operationally relevant metrics for shipowners and retrofit designers. By coupling full-scale CFD-derived aerodynamic data with realistic environmental conditions, this work offers a more accurate and actionable evaluation of the power-saving potential of rotor sail systems under real service scenarios.

Specifically, the present study conducts high-fidelity unsteady RANS simulations on a full-scale VLOC equipped with multiple rotor sails, developing thrust and drag polar diagrams across a wide range of apparent wind angles and speeds. These polar results are then incorporated into a ship performance framework to simulate power savings over representative trade routes using ERA5 wind data. First, the optimal rotor operating speed (RPM) is identified based on maximizing aerodynamic efficiency without incurring excessive drag or power consumption. Next, the derived aerodynamic forces are mapped to power-saving polar charts, illustrating the net power contribution achievable under varying environmental conditions. Finally, using these charts, projected power savings on different routes are compared, revealing how route-specific wind patterns influence rotor sail performance.

Overall, the study demonstrates that by integrating full-scale CFD simulations with voyage-specific environmental profiles, it is possible to obtain more accurate and operationally meaningful predictions of wind-assisted propulsion benefits. The findings validate the rotor sail’s potential to reduce power consumption on large ore carriers and provide actionable insights for ship operators and designers, thereby bridging the gap between conceptual estimates and real-world operational performance. This work contributes to the advancement of wind-assisted propulsion technologies and supports the broader decarbonization objectives of the maritime industry.

2. Numerical methodology

1. Computational domain and boundary conditions

The computational domain was constructed around a DWT 324,000-ton Very Large Ore Carrier (VLOC) equipped with five Flettner rotors installed along the ship's centerline. Each rotor has a diameter of 4 m and a height of 24 m. The endplate of each rotor has a diameter of 6 m and a thickness of 0.35 m. The overall ship geometry and the configuration of the computational domain are illustrated in Figure 1 and 2. Velocity inlets were defined at the front, left, right, and top boundaries of the domain, while a pressure outlet was applied at the rear boundary. The bottom boundary was set as a symmetry plane. A fully developed Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) profile was applied at the velocity inlets. The ABL velocity distribution is defined as:

$$U_{ABL} = U_{ref} \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}} \right)^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where the exponent α is $1/7$ as recommended by the International Towing Tank Conference (2014) [6], the z_{ref} is the reference height set at 10 m and U_{ref} is the wind speed at the reference height.

Figure 1. 3D model of the vessel used in this study

Figure 2. Computational domain and boundary conditions

2. Simulation setup

To evaluate the power saving performance of Flettner rotors installed on the upper deck of the ship, the Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equation is solved using commercial software STAR-CCM+ 18.06. The finite volume method is used to discretize the URANS. The Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equation (SIMPLE) algorithm is adopted for velocity and pressure coupling [7]. A second order upwind scheme is used for the discretization of convection term and a first order forward Euler scheme for the temporal discretization is used throughout all simulation. For the full-scale simulation that corresponds to fully turbulent calculation, the $k - \omega$ Shear-Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model is used to close the URANS equation [8]. The computational domain consists of a background region and an area of interest as shown in Figure 3. The background region was meshed using a hexahedral grid, which is advantageous for reducing computational time and generating low-skewness grids. In contrast, the region of interest including the rotor and the hull, where complex flow phenomena are expected, was meshed using a polyhedral grid due to its robustness in capturing intricate flow features and providing stable solutions in highly complex flow environments. (STAR-CCM+ user guide, 2023) [9]. The non-dimensional wall distance (y^+) value is set to less than 1 using the custom prism layer. It is important to recognize that the simulation time step is influenced by the RPM of the rotor. To ensure the stability of the numerical method, the time step must satisfy a constraint on the maximum cell-based Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number [10]. Consequently, as the angular velocity increases, the allowable time-step decreases.

Figure 3. Hybrid grid system

3. Verification and validation

3.1 Convergence test

To ensure the reliability of the numerical simulations, the grid convergence test was performed and evaluated using the Grid Convergence Index (GCI) method (Celik et al., 2008) [11], which is based on Richardson extrapolation (Richardson, 1910; Richardson and Gaunt, 1927) [12][13]. The Grid Convergence Index provides a numerical measure of the uncertainty in the grid system. The convergence test was conducted for a model-scale single Flettner Rotor at spin ratio of 1 and an aspect ratio of 5.1. Subscripts 1, 2, and 3 correspond to the fine, medium, and coarse grids, respectively. To obtain the Grid Convergence Index (GCI), the order of accuracy (p) must first be calculated. Which is expressed as follows:

$$p = \frac{1}{\ln(r_{21})} |\ln|\epsilon_{32}/\epsilon_{21}| + q|, \quad q = \ln\left(\frac{r_{21}^p - S}{r_{32}^p - S}\right), \quad (1)$$

where r is the grid refinement factor.

$$S = \text{sign}\left(\frac{\epsilon_{32}}{\epsilon_{21}}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $\epsilon_{32} = S_3 - S_2$, $\epsilon_{21} = S_2 - S_1$.

The Grid Convergence Index can be calculated as follows:

For the coarse-to-medium grid:

$$GCI_{32} = F_s \left| \frac{e_{32}}{r_{32}^p - 1} \right|, \quad (3)$$

For the medium-to-fine grid:

$$GCI_{21} = F_s \left| \frac{e_{21}}{r_{21}^p - 1} \right|, \quad (4)$$

where $e_{32} = \left| \frac{S_3 - S_2}{S_2} \right|$, $e_{21} = \left| \frac{S_2 - S_1}{S_1} \right|$, F_s is a factor of safety of 1.25 which is applied by Roache (1998) [14].

Additionally, the convergence ratio (CR) is a key parameter that indicates whether a solution is converging or diverging. It is defined as:

$$CR = \frac{\epsilon_{21}}{\epsilon_{32}}, \quad (5)$$

The Richardson extrapolated value, which represents the solution on an infinitely fine mesh is calculated as follows:

$$S_{extrapolated} = S_1 + \frac{S_1 - S_2}{r_{21}^p - 1}, \quad (6)$$

The results of convergence tests for three different grid systems are shown in Figure 4 and Table 1. The time-step for the grid convergence test was set to 0.001s to achieve a rotation of 4° per time-step. The convergence ratio was found to be between 0 and 1, indicating monotonic convergence. The lift coefficient in the medium grid was 1.375, while in the fine grid, it is 1.36. Both results were close to the extrapolated value of 1.34, with relative errors of 1.49% and 2.61%, respectively. The results are also supported by a low GCI value within 5%. Based on the results of the grid convergence tests, both the medium and the fine are considered acceptable. However, as shown in Figure 5, when the computational cost for the fine grid is approximately 1.5 times higher than that of the medium grid. Therefore, the medium grid was selected for further study.

Figure 4. Lift coefficient variation with respect to mesh refinement

Table 1. Results of the grid convergence test

Grid	C_L	$D/\Delta x$	r	GCI	CR	p	$C_{L\text{ extrapolated}}$
Fine	1.360	100	1.40	1.93%			
Medium	1.375	71	1.38	3.27%	0.6	1.6	1.34
Coarse	1.400	50	-	-			

While the grid convergence test estimates the dependency of the grid system, a time-step convergence test must be conducted to assess the dependency on time step. The time-step convergence tests were performed using the medium grid system with three different time steps, following the same GCI procedure described above. As shown in Figure 6 and Table 2, the temporal discretization error was found to be quite low, with a GCI value within 1%. Based on these results, a time-step corresponding to a rotation of 4° per time-step was considered the best compromise between computational cost and the temporal discretization error.

Figure 5. Computational time for the different grid system

Figure 6. Lift coefficient variation with respect to time-step refinement

Table 2. Result of the time-step convergence test

Grid	C_L	$Deg/\Delta t$	r	GCI	CR	p	$C_{L\text{ extrapolated}}$
Fine	1.379	2	1.93	0.27%			
Medium	1.375	4	2.00	0.64%	0.4	1.28	1.382
Coarse	1.365	8	-	-			

3.2 Validation

To assess the accuracy of the present CFD model, the simulation results were compared to the experimental data for a cylinder without end plate which has an aspect ratio of 5.1 (Badalamenti, 2008) [15]. The experimental condition used for validation corresponds to $Re = 1.9 \times 10^4$. The lift and drag coefficient were compared in various spinning ratio. Figure 7 shows the lift and drag coefficients as the function of the rotor spin ratio (SR). Spin ratio is expressed as follows:

$$SR = \frac{n\pi D}{U_\infty}, \quad (5)$$

where n is the RPM of the rotor, D is the diameter of the rotor and the U_∞ is the freestream velocity.

As shown in Figure 7, the present CFD simulation could predict well for lift coefficient in all spinning ratio. Conversely, while the trend of the drag coefficient with respect spin ratio is similar between the experiment and CFD results, a notable discrepancy has been observed. As discussed by Thouault (2012) [16], the fully turbulent calculations are not the appropriate approach at low Reynolds numbers. However, since this study focuses on high Reynolds numbers, turbulence modeling is essential. Nevertheless, due to the lack of experimental data at high Reynolds numbers, the turbulent model was applied to lower Reynolds number cases, which resulted in the observed discrepancies in drag force.

Figure 7. Validation of CFD results against experimental data

4. Result

4.1 RPM Optimization

To properly evaluate the efficiency of the rotor sail, it is essential to determine the optimal RPM. For this purpose, lift and drag coefficients are obtained for spin ratios ranging from 0 to 8 under the conditions where the rotor sail is expected to perform most efficiently, specifically, at an apparent wind angle of 90° . Using the extracted coefficients, the thrust force in the direction of motion is calculated for various spin ratios under arbitrary apparent wind speeds and angles. This thrust force is then converted into power, and the net power is derived by subtracting the power required to rotate the rotor from the power generated in the thrust direction. The RPM that yields the highest net power under given conditions is selected as the optimal RPM. Figure 8 illustrates the process of the RPM optimization.

Figure 8. Flow chart for RPM optimization

4.2 Effect of hull

(a) AWA=20°

(b) AWA=41°

(c) AWA=63°

(d) AWA=90°

(e) AWA=126°

Figure 9. Flow visualization at various AWA

Since the rotor is installed on the upper deck of the ship, the presence of the hull can alter the local flow, resulting in a potential difference between the standalone rotor performance and its actual performance onboard. Figure 9 presents the flow behavior around the rotor installation area on the plane aligned parallel to the incoming flow direction under various Apparent Wind Angle (AWA) conditions. This plane was selected because it enables the clearest observation of the hull's influence on the inflow entering the rotors, thereby providing valuable insight into the flow behavior affected by hull-rotor interactions. The visualization includes both streamlines and velocity contours. The velocity contours represent the difference between the local velocity and the ABL velocity, normalized by the inlet ABL velocity. Therefore, a contour value greater than zero indicates that the local velocity is higher than the inlet ABL velocity, while a value less than zero indicates a reduction in flow speed compared to the inlet. In the absence of the hull, the inlet ABL velocity would remain unchanged throughout the domain. The contours clearly demonstrate how the presence of the hull modifies the incoming flow. In all simulated cases, the blockage effect caused by the hull induces vortex formation and flow separation as the wind moves along and over the hull surface. As the apparent wind angle increases from 20° to 90°, the velocity contour upstream of the rotor becomes progressively redder, indicating a localized acceleration of the incoming flow toward the rotor surface. However, when the apparent wind angle exceeds 90°, the inflow velocity in front of the rotor decreases, as evidenced by the contour shifting toward the yellow. The expansion of the red region upstream suggests that the hull induces an acceleration of the approaching flow, potentially enhancing rotor performance compared to the standalone configuration. To quantitatively assess the hull's influence, as shown in Figure 10 (left), velocity profiles were extracted from a point located 5 rotor diameters upstream of the rotor center, along the same direction

as the AWA. Figure 10 (right) compares the vertical velocity distribution under different AWAs. The most significant changes in velocity occur between 30 m and 50 m in height — the typical rotor height range — and the velocity gradually recovers to the inlet ABL profile above this region. These results align with the contours in Figure 9, which show that the local velocity increases progressively as AWA increases from 20° to 90°. At AWA = 90°, the velocity near the rotor region exceeds the inlet velocity by more than 20%, which can significantly enhance rotor thrust. Such flow acceleration caused by the hull can either benefit or hinder rotor performance, depending on factors such as hull shape, freeboard height, and rotor placement. Therefore, it is essential to consider the effect of hull-induced flow disturbances during the design and installation process of rotor sails.

Figure 10. Effect of the ship hull on local flow field at various AWA

4.3 Thrust force vs lateral force

While the installation of rotors on a vessel can generate beneficial thrust, it also induces lateral forces that may negatively impact the ship's maneuverability. When significant lateral forces are produced, additional energy is required to counteract them through rudder or steering actions. Excessive lateral forces may also lead to undesired roll and yaw moments, potentially compromising the ship's stability. Therefore, in evaluating the propulsion efficiency of a rotor system, it is essential to also consider the associated lateral forces.

Figure 11 presents the relationship between thrust and lateral forces under varying TWS conditions when the vessel is advancing at its design speed, offering intuitive insight into the trade-offs between propulsion performance and maneuvering stability. Each curve represents the variation of these forces as TWA changes from 0° to 180° in 30° increments under a given TWS condition. Both thrust and lateral forces were normalized by the ship's calm water resistance (R_{calm}) to indicate the proportion of each force relative to the vessel's resistance in calm water. In this plot, the x-axis represents the lateral force, and the y-axis represents the thrust, with all values expressed in non-dimensional form. The diagonal dashed line ($y = x$) indicates the magnitudes of thrust and lateral force are equal. Points located above this line correspond to cases where the thrust exceeds the lateral force, representing more favorable operating conditions from a propulsive standpoint. As TWS increases, both the thrust and lateral forces generated by the rotors tend to increase. At $TWS \geq 20$ m/s, the thrust reaches notably high values, with some cases exceeding 60% of the vessel's R_{calm} . The maximum thrust is generally observed around $TWA = 90^\circ$, where the apparent wind direction is most favorable for rotor operation. In contrast, at $TWA = 0^\circ$ or 180° , both thrust and lateral force are minimal. This is consistent with the fact that the apparent wind aligns with or opposes the vessel's heading, reducing the rotor's aerodynamic effectiveness. The ratio between thrust and lateral force varies significantly depending on the TWA. At $TWA = 30^\circ$ and 60° , lateral forces become relatively large while thrust remains limited, indicating operating conditions that may impose a greater burden on the ship's steering system. Overall, Figure 11 provides valuable information not only regarding rotor thrust performance but also

in terms of lateral impact and maneuverability. These insights are critical for optimizing rotor operation strategies and determining appropriate installation locations, depending on the expected wind environment and navigational requirements.

Figure 11. Comparison of thrust and lateral forces under varying TWA and TWS

4.4 Power savings of RTS system for various operation conditions

To assess the propulsion performance of the rotor sail system across various wind directions, a polar chart was constructed based on CFD results. Figure 12 presents the net power output (in kW) as a function of TWA with ship's heading as zero degree. The ship speed is fixed as ship design speed 14.6 knots. The net power is calculated by summing the thrust forces generated by the five rotors, multiplying the result by the vessel's sailing speed to obtain effective power, and then dividing by a propulsive efficiency factor of 0.7. Subsequently, the power required to rotate the five rotor motors is subtracted to determine the final net power saving. Unlike non-dimensional performance metrics, this chart directly represents the usable propulsion power available to the ship under each wind condition. The polar plot reveals that the net power peaks around $TWA = 90^\circ$, where the aerodynamic contribution of the rotors is most significant, while it decreases markedly as the wind direction aligns more directly with or against the ship's heading (TWA approaching 0° or 180°). In general, the net power output increases with higher TWS, approximately in proportion to the square of the wind speed. This trend originates from the fundamental physical relationship between force and energy: aerodynamic thrust is proportional to the square of the relative wind velocity, and power is the product of force and velocity, which leads to power scaling with the cube of wind speed. However, since the vessel speed is held constant in this study, variations in net power primarily reflect changes in aerodynamic force, which scales with the square of TWS. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that when TWS increases from 20 m/s to 25 m/s, the net power does not exhibit the expected quadratic growth. This deviation is attributed to the operational limitations of the rotor RPM. At higher wind speeds, the rotational speed of the rotor motors reaches its upper threshold, restricting further increase in spin ratio. As a result, the lift and thrust generated by the rotors tend to plateau or grow at a diminished rate, leading to a sub-quadratic increase in net power. This observation underscores the importance of accounting for mechanical constraints in rotor sail performance evaluations, particularly under high wind conditions. It should be noted that the addition drag induced by leeway angles or increased rudder angles to counteract the lateral forces was not included in the calculation. While this assumption isolates aerodynamic contribution of the rotors, it may lead to a slight overestimation of the net power savings. In addition, although rotor RPM optimization considers halting rotor operation at apparent wind angles of 0° and 180° , the negative power may still be generated at those wind conditions. To avoid such negative

power, the folding and unfolding of rotors in response to unfavorable conditions could be suggested, however this approach is unlikely to be practically feasible in real operational environments.

Figure 12. Polar chart for power saving by rotor sail system (kW)

4.5 Evaluation of power saving based on general shipping route for VLOC

1. Consideration of weather probability for VLOC

Since 2018, KR has been collecting AIS data from ships entering ports and has been providing various services to clients based on this data, including voyage profile analysis and fuel consumption pattern analysis. Using AIS data from a total of 40 Ore carriers currently under KR's management, global wind scatter diagram for VLOC can be derived. As the aim of this analysis is to establish a standard for environmental data typically encountered by ships operating in open ocean conditions, AIS data that do not meet this objective were filtered out based on the following criteria. Detailed information of data filtering is shown in Table 3. About 40% of AIS data was filtered out and remained 60% of data was used for the analysis which shows density plot like Figure 13.

Table 3 Details of data filtering

Filter Step	Remained Data	Remaining Ratio
1. Raw data	740,701	100.0
2. Delete empty or unusual data	704,221	95.1
3. Delete in-port* condition	579,021	78.2
4. Delete data whose speed is lower than 5kn	527,049	71.2
5. Delete data where the water depth is shallower than -200m	439,530	59.3

*From the 'navigation status' of AIS data, we regarded ['At anchor', 'Moored', 'Aground'] as In-port condition.

Figure 13 Density plot of shipping route, KR classed ore carrier

The density plot of sea usage based on AIS data for ore carriers reveals a dominant operational route extending from Brazil—likely from major iron ore export ports such as Tubarão or Itaqui—across the South Atlantic Ocean, around the Cape of Good Hope, through the Indian Ocean, and terminating in East Asia, particularly South Korea, with possible extensions to China and Japan. This route reflects the transport of iron ore from Brazil, one of the world’s largest exporters, to support the steel industries in East Asia, notably in South Korea where companies like POSCO drive significant demand. Additionally, a secondary but notable route from Brazil to Europe is also visible, supporting the ore supply to European steel industries. In this study, as illustrated in Figure 14 below, the main shipping routes of the vessels are categorized into two: the Brazil–East Asia route (Route 1) and the Brazil–Europe route (Route 2). For each of these routes, we aim to estimate the expected power savings from the application of rotor sails.

(a) Route 1: Brazil-East Asia

(b) Route 2 : Brazil - Europe

Figure 14 Two significant shipping routes for evaluation of power savings

The wind data was derived from the ERA5 hindcast model [17]. Figure 15 shows wind scatter plots for the two primary routes—Route 1 (Brazil–East Asia) and Route 2 (Brazil–Europe)—with True Wind Angle (TWA) on the x-axis and True Wind Speed (TWS) on the y-axis. TWA is measured clockwise from the north, with 0° indicating wind from the north. These scatter plots illustrate the distribution and relationship between wind speed and direction along each route.

To better capture the detailed distribution, Figure 16 (a), (b) and 17 (a), (b) present histograms of wind speed and direction. Both routes share a dominant wind speed range of 5–10 m/s, but the Brazil–Europe route exhibits lower variability, suggesting more consistent wind conditions. In contrast, the Brazil–East Asia route shows slightly wider dispersion in wind speed.

Wind direction patterns differ clearly between the two routes. Route 1 is dominated by northwesterly winds ($\sim 330^\circ$), shaped by the influence of the South Atlantic subtropical high and southeast trade winds, which steer the flow northwestward as vessels head toward East Asia. On the other hand, Route 2 experiences prevailing northeasterly winds ($\sim 30^\circ$), a result of the northeast trade winds that aid in stable west-to-east passage across the Atlantic toward Europe.

(a) Route 1 : Brazil – East Asia (b) Route 2 : Brazil – Europe
Figure 15 Wind scatter diagram, true wind speed (TWS) vs. true wind angle (TWA)

(a) Route 1 : Brazil – East Asia (TWS)

(b) Route 2 : Brazil – Europe (TWS)

(c) Route 1 : Brazil – East Asia (AWS)

(d) Route 2 : Brazil – Europe (AWS)

Figure 16 Probability distribution of true and apparent wind speed

The previously discussed true wind conditions (TWS and TWA) do not account for the vessel's motion; in reality, the ship encounters apparent wind speed (AWS) and apparent wind angle (AWA), which are influenced by the vector sum of wind and vessel velocity. Figure 16 (c), (d) and 17 (c), (d) illustrate these characteristics, assuming a constant vessel speed of 14.6 knots. Unlike the relatively Gaussian distribution of TWS and TWA, the AWS and AWA distributions are notably irregular and strongly dependent on routing and encounter geometry, often diverging from typical statistical models. In particular, Route 2 (Brazil–Europe) shows more frequent occurrences of both high AWS conditions exceeding 15 m/s and very low AWS conditions under 5 m/s, indicating a broader range of encounter scenarios. Regarding AWA—an important factor for rotor sail performance—both routes predominantly experience following winds between 135° and 225° , but with different characteristics: Route 1 (Brazil–East Asia) shows a relatively uniform spread across this range, allowing for more stable thrust generation, whereas Route 2 exhibits a concentrated peak near 180° , suggesting more frequent direct following wind, which may enhance instantaneous efficiency but could lead to greater variability in rotor-assisted propulsion due to its narrow directional distribution.

(a) Route 1 : Brazil – East Asia (TWA)

(b) Route 2 : Brazil – Europe (TWA)

(c) Route 1 : Brazil – East Asia (AWA)

(d) Route 2 : Brazil – Europe (AWA)

Figure 17 Probability distribution of true and apparent wind angle

2. Discussion on net power saving of rotor sail system

A route-based assessment of wind-assisted propulsion performance was carried out to estimate the net power savings achievable using a rotor sail system installed on a Very Large Ore Carrier (VLOC). The analysis incorporates AIS-derived vessel positions and headings under the assumption of a fixed service speed of 14.6 knots, and accounts for instantaneous wind-ship interactions to calculate hourly power savings in kWh. While the reference vessel is a VLOC equipped with five rotor sails, the AIS data includes a broader population of ore carriers, and the study does not follow specific voyages between defined ports. As such, the results reflect general operational patterns along two major routes—Brazil–East Asia and Brazil–Europe—and provide insight into typical savings on an hourly basis, rather than total voyage consumption.

The probability distributions of these hourly net power savings are depicted in Figure 18, showing average values of approximately 283 kWh for the Brazil–East Asia route and 309 kWh for the Brazil–Europe route. The modest difference between the two is consistent with the comparable AWS and AWA profiles identified earlier. However, the variation in each distribution also emphasizes the impact of route-specific wind conditions and ship-wind encounter angles on rotor sail effectiveness. A supplementary table summarizes key statistical metrics, including the ratio of net power savings to calm-water propulsion demand. Although this ratio depends heavily on vessel size, engine power, and hull resistance, it provides a relative benchmark for evaluating rotor sail contributions under realistic voyage conditions.

Figure 18 Probability distribution net power saving of rotor sail system

Table 4 Statistical value of net power saving

		Route 1	Route 2
Region		Brazil - East Asia	Brazil - Europe
Power saving (kWh)	Mean	282.9	309.3
	Median	47.2	76.7
	Std.	638.6	662.7
Mean power saving ratio (% of calm sea propulsion)		1.8%	2.0%

5. Conclusion

This study conducted a comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis to evaluate the aerodynamic performance and power-saving potential of a rotor sail system installed on a full-scale Very Large Ore Carrier (VLOC). The simulation framework incorporated a realistic atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) profile, apparent wind conditions, rotor mechanical constraints, and aerodynamic interactions between the rotor sails and the ship hull. To ensure the reliability of the numerical results, both convergence testing and model validation against reference data were performed and confirmed prior to the main simulations.

The results indicated that the net power contribution of the rotor sails was maximized between $TWA=90^\circ$ and $TWA=120^\circ$ and the performance scaled approximately with the square of the true wind speed. However, at higher wind speeds, mechanical limitations on rotor RPM imposed constraints on the effective power generation. Additionally, the presence of the ship hull was found to locally distort the inflow velocity field, affecting the thrust generated by each rotor depending on its position and wind direction. In the present vessel configuration, the presence of the ship hull was found to induce a local acceleration of the inflow, resulting in a positive impact on rotor thrust generation and, consequently, on net power savings. However, it should be noted that different hull geometries may produce varying effects on the inflow field, potentially leading to adverse outcomes. Therefore, careful consideration of hull-induced flow modifications is essential when determining the placement and installation of rotor sails to ensure optimal performance.

Lateral forces acting on the vessel increased significantly with wind speed, raising potential concerns for maneuverability and rudder load. These findings underscore the importance of balancing power saving performance of RTS with navigational stability when designing rotor sail systems.

Route-based energy saving assessments, conducted using wind data derived from the ERA5 hindcast model, revealed average net power savings of approximately 283 kWh and 309 kWh for the Brazil–East Asia and Brazil–Europe routes, respectively. These correspond to approximately 1.8–2.0% of the vessel’s calm water propulsion power of VLOC, suggesting that rotor sails offer modest but measurable gains in energy efficiency under realistic operating conditions. The small difference in net power savings between the two routes is primarily due to the similarity in the distributions of apparent wind angle (AWA) and apparent wind speed along both shipping routes. It should be noted, however, that the overall power saving performance of the rotor sail system can vary significantly depending on the size of the vessel, the scale of its engine power, and its operational speed profile. When same rotor sail system is applied to smaller vessels, the relative power saving percentage may appear larger due to the reduced calm water resistance. Therefore, caution must be exercised when interpreting power saving ratios expressed as percentages. As this study estimates power saving effects based on hourly net power contribution for specific routes—rather than long-term or annualized averages—it provides shipowners with more immediate and route-relevant performance insights to support practical decision-making on rotor sail installation.

In summary, this research not only quantified the practical benefits and limitations of rotor sail systems under full-scale, route-specific scenarios, but also provided valuable insights into their aerodynamic behavior, design considerations, and operational implications for large commercial vessels.

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